

Comparative Effectiveness of Virtual Reality Exposure Therapy vs In Vivo Exposure
Therapy for Social Anxiety Treatment in Adolescents

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Introduction

Social anxiety disorder (SAD) is one of the most common mental health conditions among adolescents (Pelcovitz; Agora VR). Because of it, many suffer intense fear in social settings, especially situations like public speaking (Agora VR). Adolescents affected by social anxiety often see an effect on other aspects of their life, like lower academic performance and reduced social participation (Smithyman). Long-term consequences can include fewer career opportunities and limited social relationships (Pelcovitz).

Exposure therapy is the primary psychological treatment for social anxiety (Smithyman). This method repeatedly exposes individuals to anxiety-provoking situations in a controlled way (Smithyman). Traditional exposure therapy, also known as in vivo exposure, is based on direct, real-world interactions. Now, while in vivo exposure therapy is still considered effective, it still poses difficulties, mainly participant discomfort (Radak; Pelcovitz).

Virtual reality exposure therapy (VRET) has recently emerged as a more non-conventional exposure method. VRET uses immersive virtual environments to recreate anxiety-inducing scenarios (Agora VR). Therapists control these virtual situations precisely, adjusting the intensity to what each person needs (Agora VR; Radak). This method allows repeated exposure without logistical challenges or ethical concerns associated with real-life scenarios (Radak). VRET also allows for more accurate measurement of physiological responses, like heart rate, during therapy sessions (Agora VR).

Research on virtual reality therapy's effectiveness has mainly focused on adults so far (Gonçalves et al.; Freeman et al.). However, there is a chance teenagers may respond differently because of developmental factors in adolescence related to fear extinction (Pelcovitz).

Investigating VRET in adolescent populations is necessary to determine its effectiveness compared to conventional therapy.

Therefore, this study's main goal is to compare the effects of virtual reality exposure therapy to that of in vivo exposure therapy for social anxieties in teenagers aged 11-19. It is hypothesized that while VRET will produce an effective result, in vivo exposure therapy will yield signs of greater improvement in anxiety over the same time period.

Review of Literature

Search Strategies

Strategies to find sources used in this paper were procured through the use of multiple databases, primarily Gale Academic OneFile (applying a peer reviewed only search filter), Pubmed Central, Youtube (Ted Talks and informational presentations), ResearchGate, and Google Scholar.

Effectiveness of Virtual Reality Therapy in Reducing Social Anxiety

Research supports CRT's efficacy in reducing social anxiety and phobias, mainly in conjunction with CBT (Cognitive Behavioral Therapy) protocols. Studies mainly talk about how VRT offers a controlled, immersive environment that can alleviate specific social anxieties, such as public speaking anxiety, and reduce avoidance behavior. For example, a meta-analysis conducted by Mei Hui Lim and her team consisting of Vahid Aryadoust, an Associate Professor of Language Assessment at the Nanyang Technological University, and Gianluca Esposito, a researcher in developmental, biological, and clinical psychology, as part of the "Psychology and Cognitive Science" department of "Università degli Studi di Trento", examined 92 studies, and found a "statistically significant" reduction in public speaking anxiety, with effects comparable

to traditional CBT, which suggests that VRT provides a similarly effective intervention as IVET, or In Vivo Exposure therapy. (Lim et al.). Additionally, According to Christine Vincent and her team from the department of medicine of Thomas Jefferson University, VRT's controlled setting also allows therapists to create custom scenarios, making the treatment more suitable for younger patients (the target of this research paper) who may hesitate to participate in IVET (Vincent et al.).

Comparative Studies on Virtual Reality Therapy(VRET) and In Vivo exposure Therapy

Existing literature and studies provide evidence supporting both VRET and In vivo exposure therapy, posing them as effective treatments for social anxiety disorders. Recently, however, researchers have increasingly turned their attention to virtual reality therapy because of its potential to create controlled, immersive environments. However, there are still mixed findings regarding VRT's potential to match or exceed the effectiveness of IVET. PhD holder Stephane Bouchard and his team at the department of psychoeducation and psychology of the University of Quebec conducted a randomized controlled trial comparing CBT with VR-based exposure to CBT with IVET showed "Significant symptom reduction" in both groups, with VRT demonstrating some advantages in practicality and engagement. This study found that VRT resulted in better post-treatment outcomes on primary anxiety measures and was more practical in general for therapists, because of its adaptable and repeatable environment, making it a quite possibly better alternative to IVET. (Bouchard et al.) Another study, conducted by researcher Ivan Kovar of the Tomas Bata University in Zlin's Department of Automation and Control Engineering, focused on VRT's effect on children with social anxiety found positive outcomes, reporting that VR exposure resulted in anxiety reduction. However, he also noted that these improvements might not generalize to "real-world interactions" without "supplemental in vivo

sessions”, meaning that there is still some room for questioning when it comes to VRT’s standalone efficacy (Kovar).

Patient Engagement and Practicality in Therapy

One main advantage that VRT has over IVET is its potential to sustain patient engagement, among all age groups and types. The immersive nature of VR environments allow for controlled and personalized exposure to feared stimuli, encouraging adolescents who might be resistant to traditional IVET. In a qualitative study conducted by the previously mentioned Christine Vincent and team, researchers focused on examining provider perspectives, therapists reported high patient engagement and found VRT beneficial for adapting to patient needs, with 93.8% of providers recommending it as an effective therapeutic tool (Vincent et al.). Building on top of Vincent’s conclusions is Dorothy Strickland, a Samuel DeWitt Proctor Professor of Education at Rutgers, and her team, who say that VRT can be delivered cost-effectively, often requiring fewer resources than IVET which demands access to real-world settings for exposure (Strickland et al.). According to Lina Gega, a reader in mental health at the University of York, It can also be added that VRT often requires fewer “logistical resources” than IVET, which typically involves real-world settings that can be challenging to arrange and costly to access. Setting up a VR scenario for a social phobia, such as public speaking exercises, can be done entirely within a clinic, reducing expenses that would normally come with IVET sessions, because they might need a variety of live, public settings (Gega). VR scenarios can also provide repeatable and progressive exposure options, allowing patients to face their fears at various intensities and frequencies, which helps build resilience without the risk of overstimulation that can occur in uncontrolled, real-life scenarios. This flexibility makes VRET a more viable solution in many scenarios.

Limitations of VRET in Addressing Social Anxieties

There are still notable limitations of VRET. One of the biggest limitations would be its inability to fully replicate the presence of actual people, which is often the primary stressor for people with social anxiety. While VRET can simulate social situations, such as public speaking or social gatherings, these virtual scenarios often lack the unpredictability and more specifically the authentic reactions of real audiences. According to the previously mentioned Ivan Kovar, The absence of real people may hinder the activation of core social anxiety triggers, which typically arise from live feedback, judgment, or “perceived scrutiny” from others. Real social interactions involve unpredictable elements, like subtle facial expressions, body language, or spontaneous responses, factors that are limited in VR environments, thus decreasing immersion and the full “activation of social anxiety” (Kovar). This lack of real touch can make it challenging for patients to fully confront their social fears in therapy, which without a doubt reduces the overall effectiveness of VRET in preparing individuals to handle genuine social scenarios.

Research Gap

While numerous studies have already examined the effectiveness of VRET and IVET individually for treating social anxiety, there is a lack of research examining their comparative long-term effects, particularly in adolescent populations. Adolescents experience social challenges unique to their age group because of ongoing social developments, which are not really accounted for in existing VRET protocols. Although VRET provides a controlled, immersive environment for practicing social skills, as mentioned before, it may lack the effectiveness needed to fully trigger and address social fears that come as a result of real-world interactions. Current research has yet to conclusively determine whether VRET alone can

produce sustainable, real-world reductions in social anxiety or if combining it with IVET can enhance these outcomes, mainly as social anxieties evolve through adolescence specifically. For that reason, this study seeks to address this gap by investigating not only the immediate effectiveness of VRET vs IVET in reducing social anxieties in those aged from 11-19, but also examining how well improvements transfer to real-life situations over time. Filling this gap could inform best practices for integrating VR into anxiety treatments to maximize long-term success in young populations.

Methodology

Overall

This study is organized in a between-subjects experimental design. For this study, an experimental approach was used. The participants were divided into two groups, and then studied over a 4 week period. The first group received virtual reality exposure therapy, while the second group underwent in vivo exposure therapy. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected in the form of heart rate measurements and anxiety questionnaires (using the SPIN test), respectively. The aim was to measure and compare changes in heart rates and SPIN scores over multiple sessions.

Participants

This study recruited 20 students between 15 and 16 years old (as a means of median estimate that can be applied to a broader population of teenagers). These students were all randomly selected, based on self-reported anxiety symptoms, such as public speaking and peer interaction. The first group, which underwent virtual reality exposure therapy, consisted of 10 AP research students who consented to partaking in the program. The other ten, of the second group,

underwent in vivo exposure therapy, were all selected because of their status as local club owners. Because of their ownership of a club, they would already partake in weekly presentations during their meetings, so they consented to being monitored.

Equipment Used

For VRET, this study selected a software modified version Meta Quest 1, mainly because of its immersive VR quality. The headset was then connected to a discord audio call to simulate a proper audience to the most accurate degree.

Heart rates were measured with the Eurans Smart Watch 41mm, chosen for accurate heart rate monitoring, ease of use, and comfort for adolescent participants. The smartwatch collected real-time heart rate data continuously throughout each session.

To measure how the subjects themselves felt about their social anxiety related to public speaking and other aspects of social anxiety, a social phobia inventory (SPIN) test was given to measure how subjects perceived their social anxiety. SPIN questionnaires are measured out of 68 points, where a subject is asked to rate how they feel (5 categories ranging from "Not at All" to "Extremely") about different aspects of their social life and phobias. The more a score increases, the more it is considered indicative of social anxiety.

Procedures

This was made up of five therapy sessions conducted over five weeks, with sessions spaced evenly (once a week). All sessions lasted approximately 15–20 minutes.

VRET Procedure

For the VRET procedure, each of the 10 subjects filled out a SPIN test before starting any other procedures. Afterwards, they used the "speech trainer" application on Steam, paired with a Discord call consisting of five members who had no prior connection to the subject (in order to

conserve the true nature of an audience). The subjects would then each give a ten minute presentation on a different prompt each week (i.e. the impact of fake news on the older generation, or the need for moral courage in healthcare systems). The audience members were instructed to act like an ideal audience, welcoming the speaker and clapping when needed. They were also, however, instructed to interrupt the presenters occasionally to ask questions, as a way of confirming whether or not participants would be able to keep their composure and focus. Each subject was purposefully interrupted at least three times during the five week session.

Participants' heart rates were also being tracked during the presentation using the Eurans smartwatch. After the five week period ended, the subjects were asked to fill out the same SPIN test again, and their results were recorded.

In Vivo Procedure

The in vivo procedure was also fairly similar to that of the VRET procedure. Subjects initially filled out a SPIN test before any procedures, and then were monitored five times over a five-week testing period. During each monitoring session, Each participant delivered a speech lasting three to five minutes, during their club meeting. Over all the sessions, a mean of around 14 audience members were present at the meetings. However, rather than specific prompts like the VRET subjects, these participants simply presented information and updates regarding their club. Similar to VRET, however, these participants also had audience members who were instructed to interrupt during the presentation and ask questions. Each subject also wore a Eurans smartwatch for heart rate detection. At the end of the overall monitoring period, the subjects then took the SPIN test again.

Data Analysis

As for data analysis, this study analyzed heart rate measurements and SPIN anxiety scores. Both were used to compare the effectiveness of VRET to in vivo exposure therapy.

Heart Rate Data

Heart rate data was collected using the Eurans Smart Watch. In the VRET group, the average heart rate during session 1 was averaged across all subjects. The same was then done with session 5. Then, a 2 sample t-test was conducted, in order to verify that these results were statistically significant.

For each participant, the average heart rate during Session 1 (baseline) and Session 5 (final session) was calculated. The difference between those two values ($\Delta HR = \text{Session 1} - \text{Session 5}$) represented the change in physiological arousal across the treatment period. A positive value indicated a drop in anxiety over time.

A two-sample t-test was used to compare the mean heart rate changes between the VR group and the in vivo group. Because each participant's change was independent of the others, and because the population standard deviation was unknown, a z-test would not have been appropriate. The t-test was best in this case because it accounted for sample variability and small group sizes (that being $n=10$ per each group), and the fact that this study's data was roughly symmetric and groups were balanced. Significance was tested at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level.

SPIN Score Data

As for the SPIN data, since each subject had taken a test before and after the five week process, the difference of both tests was taken (initial SPIN score - final SPIN score), and using that, the relative change in anxiety was measured, where a positive number would mean that anxiety overall decreased, while a negative number would mean the opposite.

To ensure that the results of the test were once again statistically significant, a second two-sample t-test was used to compare mean SPIN score changes between the two groups. (given that, of course, each participant's score was independent of the others). Just like the heart rate data, since the sample size was small, the two-sample t-test was the more appropriate choice. Significance was tested at the $\alpha = 0.05$ level.

Ethical Considerations

Before the study began, all participants were notified of the study's purposes, procedure, and structure. For those not participating in the AP research class, a parental form was asked to be signed. For those who participated and were members of the AP research class, parental consent was not needed, but personal consent was. All subjects were given a document that had an explanation of the entire study in detail, including what type of data would be collected and what type of deadlines they would be told to meet. No identifying data was recorded. Participation was completely voluntary. This meant that students had the option to withdraw from the study at any time they needed to. All responses to all tests were completely confidential, as each subject was marked with a number that would represent their data. Both treatments posed the risk of typical public speaking anxieties, so as stated before, all presenters were notified and informed of the possible effects of social anxieties.

Findings

After the five weeks of exposure therapy, all the data was compiled into a google sheets spreadsheet, in order to be graphed. As previously mentioned, there were two measures used: heart rate (HR) as a physiological indicator, and SPIN scores as a psychological indicator. Figures 1 and 2 show the comparative results in these two categories, respectively. Figure 1 shows and compares the changes in heart rate between the two treatments. To be more specific,

this part of the data collection focused on how anxiety reduced based on physical indicators. As can be seen in figure 1, the in vivo exposure group saw a noticeable decrease, dropping from a 99.3 bpm average across all subjects in Session 1 to an average of 87.9 bpm in Session 5. Using the formula before (Session 1 - Session 5 = improvement), the average improvement among all IVET groups was 11.4 bpm. Along with this, the standard deviation was relatively small, with a value of 1.26, meaning that most participants had similar results, showing that the results of one person can be generalized to rest in this case. In other words, this proves the consistency of the treatments. The VRET treatment, however, did not show as much improvement. As can be seen in figure 1, the VRET group saw a decrease, but it was one that was no nowhere near the scale of the IVET group. The VRET group, however, did not show nearly as much improvement. The average heart rates in this group went from 86.6 in session one to 84.4 bpm in session five, which when using the formula for change in heart rate yields a value of 2.2 bpm. Since this is a positive value, it can still be considered an improvement in social anxiety, and a reduction in heart rate overall.

Participant ID	Session 1 HR	Session 5 HR	Difference
VR-1	91	88	3
VR-2	85	82	3
VR-3	88	86	2
VR-4	89	84	5
VR-5	85	82	3
VR-6	82	85	-3
VR-7	88	86	2
VR-8	93	90	3
VR-9	79	77	2
VR-10	86	84	2
Average	86.6	84.4	2.2
Standard Deviation	4.141926551	3.596294389	2.043961296

Participant ID	Session 1 HR (bpm)	Session 5 HR (bpm)	Difference
IV-1	98	87	11
IV-2	100	89	11
IV-3	95	85	10
IV-4	110	96	14
IV-5	99	88	11
IV-6	102	90	12
IV-7	96	85	11
IV-8	101	88	13
IV-9	97	86	11
IV-10	95	85	10
Average	99.3	87.9	11.4
Standard Deviation	4.473378042	3.348299734	1.264911064

Figure 1. Comparative HR results between VRET and IV treatments

The SPIN scores shown in Figure 2 were recorded to support these physical findings with psychological data. As shown in figure 2, the in vivo teenagers had their SPIN scores decrease by an average of 16.8 points from Session 1 to Session 5. This pattern can also be seen in the IVET bar graph, with each subject seeing great improvements and little variation among their results, with a standard deviation of 1.32. The VRET group, on the other hand, did not experience as much improvement. This group's scores only decreased by 2.9 points on average, and that too with a greater standard deviation of 1.73, meaning that this method is not always consistent in producing results. The bar graphs can also be used to show this inconsistency, as VR-6 in figure 2 actually experienced an increased SPIN score.

Figure 2. Comparative SPIN results between VRET and IV treatments

Next, a t-test was conducted in order to ensure that these results for both the differences in heart rate and SPIN tests were statistically significant. To do this, two-sample independent t-tests were conducted, and a p-value was found for both. In statistics, when a significance test is conducted, the p-value represents the chance of a certain sample occurring assuming that a certain claim is true. In this case, that claim would be that there is no significant difference in the reduction of heart rate between participants in the in vivo group and those in the VRET group. The heart rate comparison in this case yielded a critical t-value of 12.10, and a very low p-value, where $p < 0.1 \times 10^{-8}$. In the case of the SPIN score comparison, the t-test yielded a critical value of 21.45, and another extremely low p-value, that being $p < 0.3 \times 10^{-13}$. In this experiment, it can be concluded that the initial claim can be rejected, meaning that this study without a doubt provides convincing evidence that there is a difference between the two groups in anxiety effectiveness.

Discussion of Results

This study yielded results that seem to indicate a clear difference in effectiveness of the two methodologies. Across both physiological data and psychological measures, the IVET group showed consistently greater and more stable improvements compared to the VRET group.

One observation that can be used to prove this point was the difference in variability between the two groups. IVET yielded results that can be considered to show generally uniform decreases in both heart rate and SPIN scores over the 5 weeks. However, the VRET group showed greater variability in their responses. As can be seen in the VRET group, since the variability observed was higher than expected, it may suggest that virtual reality therapy doesn't consistently replicate the emotional and physiological intensity of real-world public speaking

situations. It's also important to note that the one main part of exposure therapy that makes it such a considerably effective method is its effects in invoking such responses using that situational pressure. As mentioned before, subject VR-6 even experienced an increase in anxiety, which in this scenario can almost certainly be attributed to the high variability. To add on to this, subject VR-3 commented that "It felt fake. I knew I was just in your room with a headset on, so it didn't really feel intense". VR-9 also noted that "Even though I could hear [...] audio, I couldn't do things like read their body language, for example, which I honestly felt like made it easier to ignore them rather than a real audience". This leads to the conclusion that there is a sort of emotional disconnect in virtual environments, and that the same cannot be said for IVET.

Limitations

Several ended up affecting the true power of the results in this study. Among those include sample size (which leads to generalizability), instrumentation, and potential biases.

One of the most impactful limitations of this study is the fact that this trial included a small sample size of 20 participants, that too being 10 assigned to each treatment group. Although there were still t-tests conducted in order to confirm the differences in results' statistical significance, it's important to note that small sample sizes can still increase the possibility of type I and type II errors, reducing the power of the test overall. This means that the test could possibly be understating or overstating the true difference in results. Additionally, while this study aimed to generalize results to adolescents (meaning ages 11-19), it only used adolescents aged from 15 to 17 years old, and subjects who came from similar educational and socioeconomic backgrounds, primarily recruited from one region. This means that the results of this study cannot be generalized to a larger population that isn't similar to the subjects in this study.

The instruments used in this study, while accessible and appropriate for this project's scope, most likely also had a strong effect on the outcome of this experiment. The Eurans Smartwatch is considered consumer-grade device rather than clinical-grade equipment. This means this device had a chance of producing inaccuracies in heart rates, and sometimes data that was not completely precise. Along with that, the SPIN survey, although helpful, is still a result of subjective data collected directly from the participant's view of themselves, and thus, inherently relies on the participants degree of self awareness and honesty to oneself. For this reason, there is a chance that response bias may have affected the results of the surveys. It's also important to note there are certain external conditions that may have affected participants that this study could not control. For example, school events, exams, or family sessions during the five week session could have impacted the heart rate levels and thus anxiety levels of participants independently of the therapy administered.

Implications and Future Research

While it's clear, based on the results of this study, that IVET is more effective than VRET when it comes to reducing social anxiety symptoms in adolescents, the results also suggest that VRET still holds practical value, possibly as an entry point for people who may be too anxious to participate in IVET immediately. This is because of the previously mentioned low-pressure environment that VRET creates.

Based on this claim, one of the most plausible and effective implications of these findings is the suggestion for development of more hybrid treatment models, in which therapy begins with VRET to reduce fear initially, then followed by IVET for more realism. Doing so combines the accessibility of VRET with the raw functionality of IVET in order to produce an effective treatment to reduce dropout rates and increase accessibility in places like school settings or

possibly third world clinical settings.

There is also a chance for these findings to influence clinical decision making. Because of VRET's growing accessibility and popularity, more and more practitioners are most likely tempted to prioritize it over traditional methods because of convenience. However, these results show evidence to prove that IVET is more effective and consistent in reaching its goal, which most likely could influence practitioners to continue using traditional IVET techniques over VRET as a first response treatment.

Based on the limitations previously mentioned, Future research should investigate more longer term effects of the treatment methods beyond the five-week period used in this study. Studies done over a longer period of time could help understand whether improvements in anxiety in both these methods are actually sustained in the long term. Along with this, it is better for future research to focus on groups with larger demographics, including things like different age ranges and socioeconomic backgrounds. Doing so could help researchers to better understand how these treatments affect different demographics in different ways.

Conclusion

Overall, it can be concluded by analyzing this data that in vivo exposure therapy is without a doubt more effective than VRET in reducing both physical and psychological social anxiety symptoms in teenagers. The fact that the in vivo exposure therapy group had yielded more consistent and scaled improvements when compared to VRET provides an obviously convincing argument that real life exposure sessions lead to more reliable long term anxiety reduction. While VRET definitely appeals to a newer majority because of its accessibility and technological appeal, this study concludes, based on the previously analyzed data, these conveniences do not compensate for its limited impact compared to in vivo exposure therapy.

These findings suggest that while VRET offers an easily accessible way for therapy treatment in relation to social anxieties, traditional in vivo therapy remains the better method for sustained anxiety reduction in adolescents.

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